

Drag reduction on a blunt body by self-adaption of rear flexibly hinged flaps

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Abstract

We study the aerodynamics of a blunt-based body with rear flexibly-hinged rigid flaps, subject to a turbulent flow of Reynolds number $Re = 12000$, under aligned and cross flow conditions with yaw angle $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 4^\circ$. To that aim, different values of the equivalent torsional stiffness are considered, to cover the range of reduced velocity $U^* = (0, 3.48]$ in water tank experiments. The effect of the angular deflection of plates on the drag and near wake flow is analyzed, experimentally and numerically. The results show that, in the range of U^* herein considered, the plates undergo an inwards quasi-static, self-adaptive deflection, which is symmetric for yaw angles $\beta = 0^\circ$ and asymmetric for $\beta = 4^\circ$. In particular, the plates feature small mean deformation angles for values of $U^* < 1$, whereas a sharp and monotonic increase of such deflection occurs for $U^* > 1$, i.e. for lower values of the hinge's stiffness, with an asymptotic trend towards the larger values of U^* . A critical value of reduced velocity of $U^* \simeq 0.96$ is obtained as the instability threshold above which plates depart from their initial equilibrium position. The progressive streamlining of the trailing edge translates into significant reductions of the associated mean drag coefficients. Thus, reductions close to 19% with respect to reference static plates configurations are obtained for the most flexible case of $U^* = 3.48$ for both $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 4^\circ$. A close inspection of the near wake reveals that the inwards progressive mean displacement of the plates yields a reduction in the recirculation bubble size. A symmetric evolution of the recirculating bubble is observed for $\beta = 0^\circ$, whereas the bubble becomes asymmetric for $\beta = 4^\circ$, with a larger leeward clockwise vortex. In both cases, the drag coefficient is shown to vary linearly with the global aspect ratio of the recirculating bubble. The analysis of the numerical results shows that the reduced extension of the recirculating bubble significantly alters the formation length and intensity of the eddies size an associated pressure. It is observed that despite the local pressure decrease in the vortices shed from the trailing edges, the plates self adaption reduces their size and prevents the eddies from entering the cavity, thus, creating a dead flow region with a consequent pressure increase at the body base.

Keywords: Drag reduction, bluff body, passive control, flexible flap, self-adaptive flap.

1. Introduction

The reduction of CO₂ and greenhouse gases emission is a fundamental problem in the fight against climate change. In this regard, it is estimated that road transport in heavy-duty vehicles, such as trucks or vans, is responsible for 62% of the global freight transport emissions (International Energy Agency Report, 2018). These kinds of vehicles, which can be considered as bluff-based bodies, are characterized by their poor aerodynamic performance, stemming from the need to maximize the load capacity and optimize unload times. As an example, more than 50% of the total power in heavy duty vehicles in a highway is invested in overcoming the aerodynamic drag (Hucho and Sovran, 1993), of which 25% is attributed to the rear part (Peng et al., 2018; Wood, 2006). The flow around these blunt-based bodies is characterized by a massive flow separation occurring

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10 at the edges, which leads to the alternate shedding of vortices and the formation of an intense wake at the rear
11 end. As a consequence, a sizeable recirculation bubble appears close to the base, which is responsible for the
12 generation of a low pressure region. Therefore, these bluff bodies present large values of drag, accompanied by
13 fluctuating side forces, originated from the vortex shedding process, what might result in structural vibrations
14 or stability and maneuverability problems (Hucho and Sovran, 1993).

15 Numerous studies have been conducted to reduce the aerodynamic forces present on these kinds of bluff
16 bodies. In fact, the use of passive wake control strategies to reduce the aerodynamic drag acting on the flow
17 dynamics at the rear end of vehicles has been extensively analyzed (see e.g. Choi et al., 2014; Szodrai, 2020).
18 Such strategies, which include flaps, vortex generators, splitter plates or rear cavities, among others, constitute
19 appealing solutions, provided their relative simplicity and the absence of external source of energy. A few of
20 these strategies are based on the modification of the size of the recirculation zone in the wake, where an increase
21 in the recirculation bubble length is directly associated to a reduction in the aerodynamic drag (Lorite-Díez
22 et al., 2020b). For example, the use of rigid rear cavities (Khalighi et al., 2001; Verzicco et al., 2002; Sanmiguel-
23 Rojas et al., 2011; Martín-Alcántara et al., 2014; Lorite-Díez et al., 2017, 2018; Bonnavion and Cadot, 2019)
24 has been shown to produce a downstream displacement of the low pressure zone, increasing the pressure at the
25 base of the body and, thus, reducing the aerodynamic drag. In addition, it has been demonstrated that these
26 devices (Choi et al., 2008), regardless of the geometry of the body, are able to weaken the amplitude of the
27 fluctuating forces on the near wake (Martín-Alcántara et al., 2014), modifying the boundary layer detachment
28 and displacing the vortex shedding downstream. However, these devices do not necessarily present an optimal
29 performance for all possible flow conditions, e.g. cross-flow as showed by Lorite-Díez et al. (2020a), what
30 limits their suitability for different real life scenarios and applications. This issue can be partially overcome
31 employing optimization methodologies (Lorite-Díez et al., 2017; Lorite-Díez et al., 2020a) or implementing
32 flexible elements.

33 The use of flexible structures constitutes an attractive alternative to rigid devices, given their ability to
34 adapt to the flow conditions and modify the rear part of the body to a more aerodynamic shape through passive
35 reconfiguration (Alben et al., 2002; García-Baena et al., 2021b). This process is widely observed in nature, for
36 example, in plants and trees (Harder et al., 2004; Zhang and Nepf, 2020), where the reconfiguration of flexible
37 parts, e.g. leaves, reduce the aerodynamic resistance and the effective area (Vogel, 1989). Nevertheless, the
38 passive reconfiguration of flexible systems has been scarcely investigated in bluff bodies (Abdi et al., 2019). In
39 the study of this fluid-structure interaction problem, the material selection is of great importance (Gosselin
40 et al., 2010). In particular, mechanical properties, such as the flexural rigidity EI , where E is the Young's
41 modulus and I is the moment of inertia with respect to the bending axis, have to be carefully chosen (García-
42 Baena et al., 2021a,b) in order to obtain a valid, viable solution. Flexible plates may undergo elastic instabilities
43 and complex vibrations that hinder the control of the wake and reduction of aerodynamic forces and require
44 thorough and deep analysis. Thus, the consideration of flexible systems characterized by a reduced number
45 of degrees-of-freedom as a first approach is justified by their simpler dynamics, given that they are also able
46 to provide passive reconfiguration and aerodynamic improvement. On that matter, most investigations focus
47 on elastically hinged systems implementing rear plates in cylinders (see e.g. Lu et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2014;
48 Assi et al., 2009). However, there are little studies with hinged plates in blunt-based bodies (most of studied
49 focus on single plate or tandem of hinged plates subject to axial flow, see e.g. Deb et al., 2020). For example,
50 Darbandi and Fouladi (2016) conducted a numerical study on the flow induced vibrations rotatory oscillations
51 of a three-element system. They reported significant variations of the oscillation magnitude for different values
52 of the hinge stiffness, for which a significant decrease in the mean drag and lift fluctuations was also found for
53 low values of the hinge stiffness. Similarly, Mazellier et al. (2012) analyzed the effect of porous rigid movable
54 flaps on the aerodynamics of a square cylinder, reporting reductions of nearly 25% for the drag coefficient.
55 Furthermore, Jiménez-González et al. (2021) studied numerically the flow-induced vibrations of a rear cavity
56 with elastically hinged rigid plates implemented at the base of a blunt body subjected to a laminar flow. The
57 amplitude, frequency and phase response of the system was investigated for different values of the reduced
58 velocity. In general, the flow-induced vibration of the plates has been shown to alter the shedding of vortices
59 and the near wake pressure. However, a proper understanding of these kinds of systems might be of help in
60 the design of improved control flexible strategies.

61 Under the above conditions, the present paper is focused on the use of a low dynamical order, adaptive
62 control system of two-degrees-of-freedom to reduce the drag of a bluff body and manipulate the wake behind
63 it, with use for both land heavy transport or ocean applications. In particular, the device consists of two

flexibly-hinged rigid plates implemented at the rear part of a D-shaped blunt body, tested in turbulent flow conditions, and designed to act as a drag reducer with damped oscillatory response. These mechanically more robust and easier to implement solutions than those which use flexible structures are able to yield comparable reductions in aerodynamic drag but circumvent the complex solid dynamics of the latter, such elastic transverse instabilities, which renders the former more appealing for engineering applications. In particular, in the present work the effect of different mechanical properties of the system on the drag, plates displacement and near wake flow will be experimentally analyzed, together with results from complementary numerical simulations. The analysis considers both aligned and cross flow conditions, which are usually more demanding in terms of drag coefficient and flow instability, but less commonly evaluated. Therefore, the paper is organized as follows. Sect. 2 presents the problem description. Next, Sect. 3 describes technical details of the experimental set-up and the numerical simulations. The experimental results are analyzed in Sect. 4 while the numerical additional results are reported in Sect. 5. Finally, the main conclusions of the research and future perspectives are outlined in Sect. 6.

2. Problem description

We study experimentally the wake behind an extruded blunt base body of height $h = 0.04$ m, length $l = 3.9h$ and width $w = 7.64h$ with a semi-ellipsoidal nose, of major-to-minor axes ratio of 2 (see Fig. 1). The model (García-Baena et al., 2021b) implements a rear cavity formed by two parallel rigid flaps of thickness $e = 0.05h$, length $l_c = 1.375h$ and density, ρ_s . The flaps are mounted employing a torsional joint, built using embedded flexible plates of calibrated thickness e_f and different materials (i.e. brass and steel), as detailed below. Thus, such rotary system of flap and flexible hinge is characterized by an effective torsional stiffness k , damping d , and the mass moment of inertia of the plate J . The values of the equivalent torsional stiffness of the flap-flexible plate system k , will be then varied parametrically by using different materials and thickness for the embedded flexible plates, providing with increasing values of flexural stiffness at the junction EI , where E is the Young's Modulus and $I = we_f^3/12$ is the moment of inertia around the axis of local bending of plates.

When subjected to a uniform fluid stream of constant velocity u_∞ , density ρ_f and viscosity μ_f , and with an incident yaw angle β , the body experiences net time-dependent drag force, $f_x(t)$, and side force $f_y(t)$, acting respectively on the body-based local x and y axes, belonging to the Cartesian coordinates Oxy , whose origin is placed at the body base, as shown in Fig. 1. Similarly, a global coordinates system $Ox_o y_o$, referred to the tank, can be also defined, which is coincident with the local system Oxy for $\beta = 0^\circ$. Hence, local forces f_x and f_y can be combined to obtain the drag force in the motion axis along the global axis x_o , $f_{x,o}$, as

$$f_{x,o} = f_x \cos \beta + f_y \sin \beta \quad (1)$$

(see e.g. Lorite-Díez et al., 2020a). In addition, the rear flaps may undergo rotary oscillations, being $\theta(t)$ the instantaneous angular displacement with respect to the center of rotation at the hinge formed by the flexible plate junction (note that the flaps are mounted with a transverse inward distance of $h_c = 0.075h$ with respect to the lateral edges of the body, what shifts slightly the center of rotation towards an inward transverse location). Since the motion is restricted to angular rotation, the displacement of leeward (top) and windward (bottom) flaps, ($i = 1$ and 2 respectively, see Fig. 1) can be modelled using a one degree-of-freedom, angular forced oscillator equation,

$$J\ddot{\theta}_i + d\dot{\theta}_i + k\theta_i = m_z, \quad (2)$$

where $\dot{\theta}_i$, and $\ddot{\theta}_i$ denote respectively the instantaneous velocity and acceleration of flap $i = 1, 2$, and m_z is the fluid moment with respect to the rotational hinge acting on the plates. Note that, sign criterion for angular displacement is as follows: counter-clockwise rotations are considered positive while clockwise rotations are negative (see Fig.1b).

A basic dimensional analysis allows identification of the non-dimensional parameters governing the fluid-structure interaction. Henceforth, all the variables will be non-dimensional, being the characteristic scales of length, velocity, time and pressure used for non-dimensionalization respectively h , u_∞ , h/u_∞ and $0.5\rho_f u_\infty^2$. Therefore, the Reynolds number is defined as

$$Re = \frac{\rho_f u_\infty h}{\mu_f}, \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Sketch of the experimental setup and the body configuration. (a) Side view of the towing tank, the carriage moves from right to left producing u_∞ in the x_o axis direction and sense. (b) Detailed top view of the blunt body of semi-ellipsoidal nose with the yaw angle β formed between the axis of symmetry of the body and the direction of flow. (c) Detailed scheme of the plates tightening system where a threaded screw embeds the flexible plates to a rigid straight cavity at the end of the body. (d) Free decay test in air for $U^* = 2.54$. Global and local coordinates systems, $(Ox_o y_o z_o)$ and $(Oxyz)$, are also depicted in (a) and (b) respectively.

whose value will be set to 12000 for the study. The corresponding dominant frequencies of the problem, f , are presented in non-dimensional form, as Strouhal numbers,

$$St = \frac{fh}{u_\infty}, \quad (4)$$

where dominant frequencies can be calculated from the Fourier transform of the corresponding time evolution. Regarding the flaps rotary displacement, the natural frequency of the system's oscillations in vacuum is thus obtained as

$$f_n = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{J}}. \quad (5)$$

The dimensionless reduced velocity of the problem can be computed as

$$U^* = \frac{u_\infty}{f_n h} = \frac{1}{St_n}, \quad (6)$$

where St_n is the natural reduced frequency or Strouhal number for $f = f_n$ (Eq. 4). Thus, the equivalent stiffness of the flap-embedded plate system k , dependent on the the flexural stiffness EI of the flexible plate, will change providing different values of the natural frequencies f_n , and consequently the reduced velocity U^* . The natural frequencies are selected to cover the range of reduced velocity $U^* = (0, 3.48]$. Moreover, any oscillation frequency f can be given as a frequency ratio with respect to the natural frequency of plates f_n , as

$$f^* = \frac{f}{f_n}. \quad (7)$$

The flexural stiffness EI of the flexible plates used to build up the elastic torsional junction, can be also given in non-dimensional form by means of the Cauchy number Ca , defined as

$$Ca = \frac{\rho_f u_\infty^2 w l_c^3}{2EI}. \quad (8)$$

Main parameters	Symbol	Definition	Value (Exp)	Value (Num)
Reynolds number	Re	$\frac{\rho_f u_\infty h}{\mu_f}$	12000	12000
Mass ratio	m^*	$\frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f}$	1.33	1.33
Reduced velocity	U^*	$\frac{u_\infty}{f_n h}$	(0, 3.48]	[0.01, 4.27]
Cauchy number	Ca	$\frac{\rho_f u_\infty^2 w l_c^3}{2EI}$	[0.007, 52.272]	[0.001, 305.1]
Yaw angle	β	(degrees)	0°, 4°	0°
Angular plate displacement	θ	(radians)	-	-
Frequency ratio	f^*	$\frac{f}{f_n}$	-	-
(Body axis) Drag coefficient	c_x	$\frac{f_x}{0.5\rho_f u_\infty^2 wh}$	-	-
(Body axis) Side coefficient	c_y	$\frac{f_y}{0.5\rho_f u_\infty^2 wh}$	-	-
(Motion axis) Global drag coefficient	$c_{x,o}$	$c_x \cos \beta + c_y \sin \beta$	-	-
Pressure coefficient	c_p	$\frac{p-p_\infty}{0.5\rho_f u_\infty^2}$	-	-

Table 1: Definition of main variables of the fluid-structure interaction problem.

122 Additionally, the dimensionless mass ratio of the system is defined as

$$m^* = \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_f}, \quad (9)$$

123 whose value will be set to $m^* = 1.33$ for the present study. Besides, the structural damping coefficient of the
124 moving system is computed as $d = 4\xi\pi f_n J$, where ξ is the decay rate that can be characterized experimentally
125 by means of free-decay tests for the flaps in air, which can be also used to estimate the natural frequency (in
126 vacuum) of the system f_n . This is illustrated in Fig. 1(d), where a typical free decay test in air of plates with
127 $U^* = 2.54$ is shown, together with the envelope of the damped oscillations. The different systems of flap and
128 flexible junction are analyzed giving similar rates, being the average value of ξ equal to 0.0225 ± 0.004 . Thus,
129 a low mass-damping coefficient is obtained, $m^*\xi = 0.03$.

130 Finally, the force is made dimensionless as

$$c_i = \frac{f_i}{0.5\rho_f u_\infty^2 wh}, \quad (10)$$

131 being c_x the time-dependent drag coefficient in the stream-wise direction, and c_y the time-dependent side force
132 normal to the body width, respectively, measured using the local coordinate system Oxy placed at the base of
133 the body. Similarly, if we consider the global coordinates system $Ox_o y_o$, referred to the tank, and not moving
134 with the body as it is yawed (see Fig. 1), the global drag force coefficient $c_{x,o}$ can be obtained making use of
135 eq. 1, being naturally $c_{x,o} = c_x$ for $\beta = 0^\circ$. In the following, the body axis drag coefficient will be referred to
136 as drag coefficient, while the motion axis drag coefficient will be referred to as global drag coefficient.

137 To complement the experimental results, and validate the permanent regime results from the towing tank,
138 an additional numerical study was performed for selected values of the reduced velocity U^* in the extended
139 range [0.01, 4.27] and nil yaw angle $\beta = 0^\circ$. The study was undertaken by means of turbulent two-dimensional
140 numerical simulations, whose results will serve also to evaluate and test the capability of such simple model
141 to retrieve major features from the fluid-interaction problem. Additionally, this study allowed to retrieve
142 information from the pressure at the wake p while extending the range of torsional stiffness to analyze the
143 limit of quasi-static self-adaption of plates. Thus, for instance, the pressure coefficient is defined as

$$c_p = \frac{p - p_\infty}{0.5\rho_f u_\infty^2}, \quad (11)$$

Foil #	Material	e_f (mm)	E (MPa)	f_n (Hz)	U^*	Ca
1	Brass	0.025	1.1×10^5	2.15	3.48	52.272
2	Steel	0.025	2.1×10^5	2.96	2.54	27.381
3	Brass	0.05	1.1×10^5	5.31	1.41	6.534
4	Steel	0.05	2.1×10^5	6.50	1.15	3.423
5	Brass	0.075	1.1×10^5	9.80	0.77	1.936
6	Brass	0.1	1.1×10^5	11.95	0.63	0.817
7	Brass	0.5	1.1×10^5	-	$\rightarrow 0$	0.007

Table 2: Main features of embedded flexible plates used in the experimental study.

where p_∞ is the pressure at the incident free-stream. The spatial average of the pressure coefficient at the base allows to obtain the base suction coefficient $c_b = -\langle c_{p,b} \rangle$. A summary of the main variables characterizing both studies is listed in Table 1.

In the following, any time-dependent variable will be denoted using lower case letters, e.g. a , while its temporal averaging will be expressed by means of capital letters, $A = \bar{a}$, unless otherwise stated. Thus, employing the Reynolds notation, $a = A + a'$, with $A' = \sqrt{\overline{(a')^2}}$ being the standard fluctuation. Besides, to evaluate the amplitude of the time-dependent variable a , we will apply the Hilbert transform to obtain the instantaneous amplitude (envelope) \hat{a} , whose time-averaged value is expressed as \hat{A} .

3. Experimental and numerical details

3.1. Experimental set-up

The experimental study consisted of series of tests performed in a 2 m long towing tank of 0.6 m x 0.6 m test section, where the body is towed from rest until reaching a permanent regime velocity of $u_\infty = 0.3$ m/s, as shown in Fig. 1 (a). The acceleration time is set to be short enough ($< 0.5s$) to ensure a long permanent regime and enough oscillation cycles of flaps for the most demanding case of largest U^* .

The 3D printed body was connected to the towing carriage using a steel shaft holding from a turntable platform, that allowed a precise alignment of the body with respect to the incident stream thus making possible to precisely vary the angle of attack β . A load cell was installed between the platform and the body to account for the drag force measurement, as shown in Fig. 1 (a). In addition, two thin acrylic plates were placed at the body ends close to the free surface and ground, to avoid any effect of the free surface waves and ground clearance. A small gap between end plates and flaps was ensured to avoid any interference during vibration. The total blockage ratio of the moving submerged system for the yawed configuration is approximately 7%, which is low enough to avoid important velocity correction, considering that the present study is fundamentally comparative.

Besides, the rear flexible-hinged flaps were installed at the body base using an add-on system that allowed to rigidly hold the metallic foils (brass or steel) with calibrated thickness e , by means of adjustable slits guided by holding screws. Using such holding system, the flexible hinges were located at a small inboard distance of $h_c = 0.075h$ with respect to the rear edges, thus ensuring that the rigid plates remain in line with the body sides. A detailed scheme of the torsional joint built using a tightening screwed system is included in Fig. 1(c). Additionally, a small gap is left between the base and flaps edges, ensuring that the system can freely rotate around the flexible plates' embedment. The gap is small enough to approximate the displacement as that of a one degree-of-freedom hinged-spring oscillator. The dynamic behavior of the system as a one degree-of-freedom oscillator is illustrated with help of Fig. 1(d), where the evolution of the angular oscillations of the plate θ during a free-decay test in air is plotted, alongside the envelope of the damped vibrations. From there, and after application of the Hilbert transform, damping ratio and natural frequency are obtained.

178 To vary the equivalent stiffness of the hinge, seven different configurations of embedded flexible plates with
179 different materials, brass and steel, and calibrated thickness ($e = 0.025, 0.05, 0.075, 0.1$ and 0.5 mm) were
180 used. Thus, the different junction configurations were initially characterized through free-decay tests in air
181 keeping the body at rest, where the angular displacement of flaps was measured to obtain respectively the
182 corresponding structural damping and natural frequency f_n of the combined flap-flexible plate system, from
183 where the value of reduced velocity U^* is computed, as defined in eq. (6). These values are listed in table 2.
184 Note that these represent averaged values for both flaps, since the free-decay tests were applied to the two
185 flaps independently. Finally, the stiffer case #7 is considered as the rigid reference, i.e. $U^* \rightarrow 0$.

186 3.2. Measurements of displacement of flaps, drag force and flow velocity

187 The flow-induced displacement of the rear flaps was recorded by means of optical laser sensors (model Leuze
188 ODSL-8/VC66-200-S12), that were towed with the body along the canal, and were installed as displayed in
189 Fig. 1. These sensors measured the linear displacement of the flaps' tips, from which, after application of
190 adequate trigonometric transformation, the instantaneous flaps' angular location θ was provided. The linear
191 resolution provided by the laser translates into an angular accuracy of 0.0005 rad.

192 Additionally force measurements were performed by means of a load cell (model SRI M3703A) placed below
193 the holding system and the body (see Fig. 1). The load cell did rotate with the body as the yaw angle was
194 modified, so that measurements were obtained in terms of the local reference system Oxy and subsequently
195 composed using eq. (1) to obtain the global drag along the motion axis x_o . The data acquisition frequency
196 was 1kHz , and 6 runs were performed for each different hinge configuration to ensure repeatability of results.
197 The accuracy of the load cell was ± 0.001 N, what corresponds to an approximate uncertainty of 0.002 for c_x .

198 In view of the reported experimental and numerical results in the literature (see e.g. Park et al., 2006;
199 Pastoor et al., 2008) and the previous studies undertaken in the same facility (e.g. Lorite-Diez et al., 2018;
200 García-Baena et al., 2021b) for similar D-shaped bodies, which reported nearly uniform flow variable distri-
201 butions along the spanwise coordinate at the base and near wake, the employed set-up used herein can be
202 considered to induce a quasi-two dimensional flow in a first approximation, specially with the use of [end plates](#)
203 at the body laterals. Thus, near-wake velocity fields in the x, y plane (2D-2C) were obtained by means of
204 time-resolved Particle Image Velocimetry (TR-PIV) at a fixed spanwise location, $z = 0$. The measurements
205 were performed using a 5 W Diode-Pumped Solid State (DPSS) green laser, that illuminated from behind
206 the body, synchronized with a CMOS-sensor, 12 bit, 1 Mpixel High-Speed Camera, located at the bottom
207 of the carriage and towed alongside the body (Fig. 1a). This set-up provided with an approximate Field of
208 View (FoV) of $3h \times 2h$ behind the body, which allowed to properly capture the near wake. The images were
209 recorded with a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels and an acquisition rate of 1000 fps (recording at least 300
210 images per vortex shedding cycle, and covering between 4 and 6 shedding cycles, depending on the value of
211 U^*). Post-processing of images was performed using the MATLAB® toolbox PIVlab (Thielicke and Stamhuis,
212 2014). To account for the differences of velocity in the region of interest, three distinct consecutive interro-
213 gation windows of respective sizes of 64×64 , 32×32 and 16×16 pixels, were used in combination with a
214 50% overlapping area. As a result, a vector field of 124×62 and a spatial resolution of $0.034h$ was obtained,
215 with the number of spurious vectors obtained being very small and always less than 1% of the total. [Thus,](#)
216 [given the high temporal resolution of our measurements and the repetitive behaviour of the vortex shedding](#)
217 [process, very smooth averaged fields were obtained.](#) In addition, the characteristic shedding frequency was
218 also acquired from transverse velocity PIV data and complementary measurements using a one-dimensional,
219 LDV system (model MSE miniLDV™). Further details on these experimental procedures and uncertainty
220 estimation of PIV measurements are provided in (García-Baena et al., 2021b).

221 All the experimental results reported herein have been computed once the permanent conditions were prop-
222 erly checked in our measurements, then, time-averaging is performed for each test. The associated uncertainties
223 and mean values are obtained from those tests performed at each U^* condition.

224 3.3. Numerical model

225 The numerical study aims to complement the previous experimental analysis at $\beta = 0^\circ$. To that aim,
226 selected values of the parameters, covering a extended range of reduced velocity $U^* = [0.01, 4.27]$ and the
227 equivalent Cauchy number $Ca = [0.001, 305.1]$ are considered. Note that, as explained below, the numerical
228 hinge is mechanically different from the experimental one, and the value of Ca cannot be computed from

any numerical flexural stiffness EI , so that values of Ca are inferred from the experimental correlation $Ca = Ca(U^*)$ and numerical values of reduced velocity U^* , which can be properly established in simulations, after computation of f_n (eq. 5).

Therefore, the fluid-structure interaction problem of the flow around the body implementing the flexible hinged plates was studied by means of 2D numerical simulations, assuming that no variation occurs in the spanwise direction. Therefore, the transient, turbulent flow of an incompressible fluid, of density ρ_f and viscosity μ_f equal to those of water, was considered, whereas the flexible junctions of the plates with the rigid body were modelled as a torsional spring of mass moment of inertia J , torsional spring stiffness k , and damping coefficient d . From here, the natural frequency of oscillation of plates was computed as detailed in eq.(5), to subsequently obtain the reduced velocity U^* (see eq. 6).

The computations were conducted using the open source CFD finite-volumes toolbox OpenFoam[®] (OpenCFD, 2016). To that aim, the solver pimpleDyMFoam, which was used in a previous work (Jiménez-González et al., 2021), was employed, implementing an Unsteady-Reynolds-Average-Navier-Stokes (U-RANS) $k-\omega$ SST model (Menter, 1994; NASA Langley Research Center and Rumsey, 2015). The plates' movement was modelled as a one angular degree-of-freedom rigid body transient motion using the 6-DoF solid-body mesh motion solver that applies SLERP interpolation of movement as function of distance to the object surface and an Arbitrary Lagrangian-Eulerian (ALE) moving mesh technique (Jasak and Tukovic, 2010). Thus, the plate's dynamics was considered as an angular forced oscillator (eq. 2), with the center of rotation being the hinge-like junction located at the body rear, as in Jiménez-González et al. (2021) (only a pair of fluid numerical cells are set between the base of the main body and the plate to prevent numerically the flow between the two sides of the plate and to create some space to avoid the physical interference between solid base and moving plates in their oscillation). The experimentally determined values of J and d were used as input parameters, while k was selected and varied to provide with different values of U^* within the range defined in Table 1. Second-order discretization schemes were used both in space and time. The PIMPLE algorithm was used for the pressure-velocity coupling (OpenCFD, 2016), which is suitable to solve transient problems of relatively high Courant numbers. The body motion was solved through an ALE algorithm, that allows to compute the displacement and velocity fields from the moving plates (moving boundaries). The solver deforms the mesh region affected by the plates motion following a Laplace equation, applied to the cell displacement, in such a way that the level of mesh deformation is controlled by means of a diffusivity coefficient in the Laplacian term (Jasak and Tukovic, 2007). Finally, numerical stability was ensured by limiting the time step to obtain a maximum Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number of 0.2 (which yielded maximum dimensionless time steps smaller than $\Delta t \simeq 5 \times 10^{-3}$).

The computational domain reproduces the experimental set-up (Fig.1), i.e. a blunt base body with rounded nose of height h and length l , implementing two hinged parallel rigid flaps of thickness e , length l_c and density ρ_s , surrounded by a fluid of density ρ_f and viscosity μ_f those of water. The global dimensions of the rectangular domain were selected to assure no influence of the boundaries on the solution, as in Jiménez-González et al. (2021). In particular, the body was placed at the half-height of the domain, of total height $21h$ and at a length of $10h$ downstream from the inlet, and $30h$ upstream from the outlet. Appropriate conditions were imposed at the boundaries, namely, a uniform free stream flow of velocity $(u_\infty, 0, 0)$ and turbulence intensity 0.5% at the inlet, outflow conditions at the outlet, i.e. $\mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} = 0$ and $p = 0$, slip condition at the laterals, $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$ and $\partial p / \partial n = 0$, and no-slip condition at the body. In the previous expressions \mathbf{n} is the outward normal. The computational mesh consisted of a staggered grid, where a stretching was performed near the body and plates, to make sure that $y^+ < 1$, and the wake region is fine enough to resolve the flow with the right spatial resolution (see Fig. 2a,b). The numerical simulations for the different values of U^* were conducted using a converged solution for the base case with rigid plates ($U^* = 0$) as initial condition, obtained after 30 shedding cycles once the permanent regime is reached. Then, the joint stiffness was changed to match the desired U^* and the simulations were run until a sufficiently long period of the corresponding permanent regime is obtained (see Fig. 2c). Finally, the mesh used was selected as a result of a grid convergence study, which was conducted to ensure the grid-size independence of the results. To that end, different simulations were sequentially performed with an increasing number of grid points, starting from a coarse grid with 0.5×10^5 computational cells, see table 3, for the case of the flow around the body implementing a cavity with the most flexible jointed rotating plates, i.e. $U^* = 4.27$. In comparing results corresponding to different grids, the forces acting on the body were characterized by the time-averaged drag coefficient C_x , and the plates mean angle of rotation Θ . The refinement was continued until the relative difference resulting from consecutive meshes was

283 less than 1.5% for the drag coefficient and less than 2.5% for the mean angle of rotation, see table 4. Thus,
 284 mesh #4 (with 2×10^5 cells) was finally used in our simulations. For further details on the methods and
 285 complementary studies, the reader is referred to Jiménez-González et al. (2021).

Figure 2: Grid distribution employed in the numerical simulations: (a) general view and (b) closer view of the grid around the plate. Red dot in (b) represents the hinge location. (c) Temporal evolution of the drag coefficient and plates deflection for $U^* = 1.15$, starting from the converged solution of the base case with rigid plates. Drag coefficient in black dashed line and deflection angles for both plates: θ_2 in dark gray and θ_1 in light gray. Note that, sign criterion for angular displacement is as follows: counter-clockwise rotations are considered positive while clockwise rotations are negative. Given that, both plates will approach each other moving towards inner transverse locations when the lower plate displacement θ_2 is positive and the the upper plate displacement is negative θ_1 .

Mesh	n_x	n_y	N	Δx	Δy
#1	264	194	$\sim 0.5 \cdot 10^5$	$0.019h$	$0.03h$
#2	372	274	$\sim 1 \cdot 10^5$	$0.016h$	$0.022h$
#3	454	334	$\sim 1.5 \cdot 10^5$	$0.014h$	$0.018h$
#4	524	386	$\sim 2 \cdot 10^5$	$0.012h$	$0.014h$

Table 3: Meshes used in the grid convergence study: #1 coarse, #2 medium, #3 fine and #4 very fine: n_x and n_y denote respectively total number of nodes in x and y directions, N is the grid size, while Δx and Δy are the characteristic grid resolution in the near wake region.

286 In the numerical results shown next, the averaged fields are obtained once the flow reaches a permanent
 287 regime. Thus, the averaged flow fields are computed using the instantaneous pressure and velocity fields at
 288 each time step. For force coefficients and plate deflection, their values are stored at each time step, being their
 289 averaged values obtained through post-processing. This temporal average is computed through 20-40 vortex
 290 shedding cycles with around 700 (depending on the vortex shedding frequency of the particular case) time
 291 steps per cycle.

Mesh	C_x	$\epsilon_{j,j+1}$ (%)	St_w	$\epsilon_{j,j+1}$ (%)	Θ	$\epsilon_{j,j+1}$ (%)
#1	0.505	6.10	0.280	4.437	6.685	8.81
#2	0.537	2.26	0.293	-	6.143	4.55
#3	0.550	1.38	0.293	-	5.864	2.13
#4	0.558	-	0.293	-	5.741	-

Table 4: Grid convergence study for a blunt-based body with a cavity with the most flexible jointed rotating plates, $U^* = 4.27$ at $Re = 12000$, using four different meshes (#1 coarse, #2 intermediate, #3 fine and #4 very fine) based on the time-averaged drag, C_x , characteristic Strouhal number of the periodic vortex shedding at the wake, St_w , and the mean deflection of the plates adaption, Θ . Also shown is the relative error $\epsilon_{j,j+1}$ (%) = $|V(j+1) - V(j)|/V(j) \times 100$, where V is the corresponding variable.

4. Experimental results

4.1. Analysis of the permanent regime

The analysis of the time-dependent variables is performed within a selected analysis window of the steady regime of the flow. In particular, as described by García-Baena et al. (2021b), the typical time-evolution of drag force corresponding to a body that is initially accelerated from rest and stopped at the end of the run displays two added mass peaks associated respectively to the acceleration and the final deceleration of the towed carriage, and a steady regime in between them. The results of body axis drag coefficient (in the following drag coefficient) c_x and plates' displacement θ for a typical run are illustrated in Fig. 3, for a reduced velocity of $U^* = 1.41$ and $\beta = 0^\circ$. As observed, after a short transient a steady regime is established, characterized by a seemingly sinusoidal oscillation of plates and a nearly constant value of drag. The limits of the analysis window were selected to ensure statistical convergence of the standard deviation of the drag using moving averages of 0.3 s, and to include at minimum of 4 cycles of plates' oscillations. A further discussion on whether the run length is sufficient to provide a steady drag value can be found in García-Baena et al. (2021b) (note that a similar facility is employed in Satheesh and Huera-Huarte, 2019). Finally, at least 6 runs were performed for each value of U^* to ensure repeatability of the results. In addition, some initial tests were run in a water channel facility, available originally at the laboratory (dimensions of test section are 2.5 m \times 0.4 m \times 0.4 m), with a steady body to validate the towing tank results for selected values of U^* . Relative errors for the drag force and amplitude and frequency of plates' oscillations were found to be smaller than 4.1% for all cases (note that such errors may be related to constructive and geometrical differences between both facilities). Additional validation of the permanent regime of the flow was also performed computing the permanent run length and comparing it with other validated permanent values reported in the literature for towing facilities testing bluff bodies (see e.g. previous work from the authors García-Baena et al., 2021b, and references therein).

Figure 3 illustrates the use of the statistical algorithm defined to find the steady regime window and its limits. Thus, the start time t_i of the window and the end time t_f for the drag force $f_x(t)$ are shown values of t_i and t_f may be sensitive to increase in the reduced velocity, widening the selected time interval). In the selected window the drag force $f_x(t)$ is averaged, which allows to calculate the average drag coefficient C_x for all cases analyzed. Similarly, during the analysis window of the permanent regime of drag force, the displacement of plates is analyzed, as shown in Fig. 3. Note that, following the sign criterion given in Sect. 2, both plates will approach each other moving towards inner transverse locations when the upper (leeward) plate displacement θ_1 is negative and the lower (windward) plate displacement is positive θ_2 (see Fig. 1b). As observed in Fig. 3, the displacement of both plates, display in-phase harmonic oscillations over a mean location, which is shifted with respect to the initial position at rest. This average location of plates is computed as the mean value of the displacement signals, Θ , and shown for illustration purposes using dashed lines in Fig. 3. In view of the sign of both plates' displacement (θ_2 is positive while θ_1 is negative), they move towards inner locations once the flow is set, so that the plates come closer in average, making the trailing edge more aerodynamic. Additionally, the amplitude of oscillations is obtained by means of the Hilbert transform, which identifies envelope of signals, from which the averaged value $\hat{\Theta}$ is computed. In addition, frequency of oscillations may be obtained through spectral analysis by taking the Power Spectral Density of signals. To ensure enough spectral resolution, at least

Figure 3: Experimental measurements of drag force and plates' angle of displacement for $U^* = 1.41$ and $\beta = 0^\circ$. The analysis window of steady regime of drag force (dashed-dotted black line) and displacement angle of plates (light gray solid line - upper plate displacement θ_1 ; dark gray solid line - lower plate displacement θ_2 , see Fig. 1) and corresponding average values Θ (dashed gray lines), lying between limits t_i and t_f defined with vertical lines. Simplified sketches of the displacement of plates during acceleration and deceleration are also included for illustration purposes.

330 four cycles are captured within the window for all the values of U^* . Finally, note that some simplified sketches
 331 of the relative location of plates at different stages of the towed motion have been included for illustration
 332 purposes and clarity of interpretation of results during acceleration and deceleration stages, i.e. plates are
 333 shown to approach each other during acceleration, and separate during deceleration.

334 4.2. Drag force

335 Figure 4(a) displays the evolution of experimental time-average values of drag coefficient C_x and the global
 336 drag coefficient $C_{x,o}$ with the reduced velocity U^* , for yaw angles $\beta = 0^\circ$ and 4° . The associated uncertainty
 337 is also included, which is found to be lower than 2.4% in all cases. It is shown that values of C_x ($\beta = 4^\circ$) are
 338 higher than those of C_x ($\beta = 0^\circ$), as expected from a presumably more abrupt flow separation at the rear under
 339 cross-flow (Lorite-Díez et al., 2020a). In general, regardless of the value of β , as the reduced velocity increases
 340 (the stiffness of flexible hinges decreases) for $U^* < 1$, the drag C_x is only slightly reduced, and the trends
 341 display similar plateaus. However, for $U^* > 1$ the drag coefficient reduces abruptly, showing a monotonous
 342 decrease in both cases. It should be noted that, both curves are nearly parallel for low values of U^* , but they
 343 approach at higher values of U^* , indicating that the reduction in drag induced by flexibly hinged plates is
 344 more efficient under cross-flow than for aligned conditions. To quantify these drag reductions, we present in
 345 Fig. 4(b) the corresponding relative variations with respect to the reference cases of rigid plates (case #7 in
 346 table 2) for both yaw angle values, i.e. $C_{x,ref}(\beta = 0^\circ) = 0.698$ and $C_{x,ref}(\beta = 4^\circ) = 0.723$. As observed,
 347 similar relative reductions are attained, with maximum values being approximately 18% and 19% for $\beta = 0^\circ$
 348 and 4° respectively.

349 In addition, when the global drag coefficient along the motion axis x_o is considered, similar trends to those
 350 obtained at $\beta = 0^\circ$ are observed for $\Delta C_{x,o}(\beta = 4^\circ)$ in Fig. 4(b), with nearly identical maximum reductions with
 351 respect to the reference static case (note that $C_x(\beta = 0^\circ) = C_{x,o}(\beta = 0^\circ)$). However, important quantitative
 352 differences are observed in values of $C_{x,o}$ on account of the effect of the local side force C_y (see eq. 1). Under
 353 aligned conditions, the side force is nil due to the symmetry of the configuration, and it does not affect the
 354 drag. However, at $\beta = 4^\circ$, the yaw induces transverse pressure gradient between both sides of the body, in
 355 such a way that the static case ($U^* \rightarrow 0$) features a lateral coefficient of $C_y \simeq 1.35$, while it decreases with
 356 increasing U^* , until reaching values close to 1 for $U^* > 2.54$, as the plates readapt to flow. Consequently, as
 357 depicted in Fig. 4(a), the composed global drag becomes $C_{x,o} = 0.816$ for $U^* \rightarrow 0$, but decreases with U^*
 358 reaching $C_{x,o} = 0.66$ for $U^* = 3.48$. Notwithstanding the foregoing, the global drag presents a local increase
 359 for $U^* = 1.41$, which will be shown below to coincide with the peak of fluctuating amplitude of plates, that
 360 seems to alter the pressure gradients existing between windward (positive pressure) and leeward sides (negative
 361 pressure) at the rear part of the body, and therefore, enhances the side force. In any case, such increase in
 362 global drag is soon reverted as U^* increases above such value, providing a maximum relative reduction of

Figure 4: Evolution with the U^* as a function of the yaw angle β of (a) time average drag coefficient C_x and global drag coefficient $C_{x,o}$ for $\beta = 4^\circ$, where experimental uncertainties are included with error bars, and (b) corresponding relative percentage variation of C_x and $C_{x,o}$ with respect to the reference rigid case, ΔC_x and $\Delta C_{x,o}$. (c) Evolution of the estimate of equivalent Vogel exponent as a function of the Cauchy number Ca for experiments with $\beta = 0^\circ$. Dotted symbols represent experimental values, while numerical results are displayed using asterisks. In (c) dotted line represents numerical estimation of γ for the extended range of Ca . Evolution with the U^* as a function of the yaw angle β of (a) time average drag coefficient C_x and global drag coefficient $C_{x,o}$ for $\beta = 4^\circ$, (b) corresponding relative percentage variation of C_x and $C_{x,o}$ with respect to the reference rigid case, ΔC_x and $\Delta C_{x,o}$. (c) Evolution of the estimate of equivalent Vogel exponent as a function of the Cauchy number Ca for experiments with $\beta = 0^\circ$. Dotted symbols represent experimental values, while numerical results are displayed using asterisks. In (c) solid line represents numerical estimation of γ for the extended range of Ca .

363 $\Delta C_{x,o} \simeq 20\%$, as plotted in Fig. 4(b). Thus, it is evident that the performance of flexibly mounted flaps is
 364 preserved in terms of drag reduction, under cross-flow conditions. This represents an advantage over classical
 365 rigid rear cavities, whose efficiency as drag reducers is considerably hindered under cross-flow (Lorite-Díez
 366 et al., 2020a). This result may open up applicative perspective in applications involving bluff vehicles.

367 The strong reduction displayed by the mean drag force suggests that deflection of flexibly-hinged flaps is
 368 taking place as the reduced velocity increases, whereby plates approach each other progressively. Following
 369 a previous work from the same team (García-Baena et al., 2021b), and inspired in reconfiguration of pure
 370 flexible elements, the influence of such process on the drag can be quantified by means of the Vogel exponent
 371 γ computation. In particular, the classical quadratic velocity-drag law at large Re for rigid bodies $F_x \propto U^2$
 372 is modified to a smaller power law $F_x \propto U^{2+\gamma}$, with γ being the Vogel exponent that takes typically negative
 373 values (0 and -1 indicate, respectively, quadratic and linear relationships between velocity and drag). Thus,
 374 the value of γ has been traditionally employed in problems concerning flexible plates placed transversely to
 375 the flow stream, to evaluate the effective front area reduction and the streamlining of the body for different
 376 shearing flows. However, as highlighted by García-Baena et al. (2021b), for the current configuration, the
 377 value of γ may be used to evaluate the effect of the rear reconfiguration on the recirculation bubble size. To
 378 that aim, the Vogel exponent is computed using the following expression

$$\gamma = 2 \frac{\partial \ln \Re}{\partial \ln Ca}, \quad (12)$$

379 where $\Re = C_x/C_{x,ref}$ is the reconfiguration number and Ca is the Cauchy number given for each flexible plates'
 380 hinge in table 2. The evolution of the experimental Vogel exponent with Ca is depicted in Fig. 4(c) at aligned
 381 flow conditions $\beta = 0^\circ$. In particular, it can be observed that $\gamma \simeq 0$ for low Cauchy number, but displays
 382 negative values for $Ca > 3.423$ ($U^* > 1.154$), from where the quadratic law $F_x \propto U_\infty^2$ no longer holds. The
 383 exponent displays an experimental minimum value of -0.21 at $Ca = 52.272$, which is the the most flexible case
 384 investigated in experiments. As it will be discussed below, numerical simulations allow a first approximation on
 385 the extrapolation of the Vogel exponent computation towards higher values of Ca (see dotted line in Fig. 4c).
 386 This estimation shows an increase of γ to reach -0.06 at the maximum Ca investigated numerically, indicating
 387 a limit on the potential decrease of the drag force with the increase of flexibility. This trend resembles that
 388 obtained for rear flexible foils by García-Baena et al. (2021b) and suggest a similar self-adaptive process in
 389 spite of the mechanical differences between adaptive flaps.

Figure 5: Evolution with the reduced velocity U^* of (a) mean angular displacement (inwards) of plates Θ and mean amplitude of angular oscillations of plates $\hat{\Theta}$, where experimental uncertainties are included as error bars; (b) square of the time-average angular position Θ^2 ; (c) frequency ratio $f^* = f_p/f_n$ of plates oscillations; and (d) detail of the mean amplitude of angular oscillations of plates $\hat{\Theta}$, for $\beta = 0$, as shown in (a). In order to represent experimental results in: grey ($\beta = 0^\circ$), red ($\beta = 4^\circ$, windward plate) and blue ($\beta = 4^\circ$, leeward plate) circles are used for Θ while points (with dashed lines) are used for $\hat{\Theta}$. Numerical results ($\beta = 0^\circ$) are displayed using asterisks and solid lines. Solid line in (b) represents the linear fit $\Theta^2 = C_f \cdot (U^* - U_{cr}^*)$, while the solid and dashed lines in (c) represent respectively the Strouhal law vs U^* , given by the reference rigid cavity body $f^* = St_w^r \cdot U^*$, and its harmonic $f^* = 2 St_w^r \cdot U^*$, with $St_w^r = 0.29$.

390 4.3. Plates displacement

391 Laser measurements have been used to determine the mean angular displacement (inwards) of both flaps
392 and to characterize their corresponding average position Θ and amplitude of oscillations $\hat{\Theta}$ within the analysis
393 window for the permanent regime. As discussed earlier with help of Fig. 3, both plates oscillate in phase around
394 mean transverse positions, which are shifted transversely inwards as the value of U^* grows. As a result, the
395 plates undergo symmetric time-average angular displacements, and anti-symmetric (in-phase) instantaneous
396 oscillations. Fig. 5(a) displays experimental mean results of both plates for Θ and $\hat{\Theta}$, the latter also shown
397 in Fig. 5(d) for the sake of clarity. The uncertainty corresponding to the measurements of Θ and $\hat{\Theta}$ is also
398 included. As observed, the mean angle Θ shows very low values for $U^* < 1$, meaning that there is little
399 adaption of plates for the stiffer cases of the study. However, for $U^* \geq 1$ there is a sharp increase of the
400 mean angular displacement, that attains a maximum value of 5.7° for the largest U^* investigated. Thus, the
401 trailing cavity defined by flaps becomes progressively more aerodynamic as the stiffness of hinges is reduced,
402 that translates into corresponding reductions of the mean drag coefficient, as illustrated earlier with help of
403 Fig. 4(a). Finally, the mean deflection seems to reach an asymptotic trend at large U^* (noticeable if numerical
404 results are considered, see asterisks in Fig. 5), what may define a practical limit on the self-adaption of plates,
405 and associated drag reduction. This observation is consistent with the increase of the Vogel exponent depicted
406 in Fig. 4(c).

407 The abrupt increase of the mean angular displacement of plates suggest the occurrence of a bifurcation
408 related to the existence of a critical reduced velocity, i.e. critical effective hinge stiffness, above which plates
409 deflect from their initial equilibrium position. A quantification of such an instability threshold can be obtained,
410 e.g. by using the classical normal form of a pitchfork bifurcation, which is typically used in dynamical systems
411 to predict the departure of unstable dynamics from equilibrium close to the bifurcation (see e.g. Jiménez-
412 González, 2013). To that aim, the square of the mean angular displacement is displayed in Fig. 5(b), where
413 it can be observed that Θ^2 features a linear trend with U^* . Hence, the linear fit $\Theta^2 = C_f \cdot (U^* - U_{cr}^*)$ can
414 be applied to data (solid line in Fig. 5b), with C_f being a fitting constant and U_{cr}^* the critical threshold of
415 instability. The linear extrapolation of Θ^2 to zero gives a value of $U_{cr}^* \simeq 0.96$.

416 Additionally, the mean amplitude of flaps oscillations $\hat{\Theta}$ is depicted in Fig. 5(a,d). As observed, the flow-
417 induced oscillations of flaps are of moderate amplitude within the whole range of U^* investigated. In particular,
418 the dynamic response of flaps seems to be similar to the classical three branches (with different amplitudes)

Figure 6: Time-averaged contours of axial velocity $U_x(x, y)$ and corresponding streamlines for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and (a) $U^* = 0$, (b) $U^* = 1.154$, (c) $U^* = 3.48$. An estimation of flaps location and orientation has been included for illustration purposes.

419 response in canonical VIV problems, i.e. initial ($U^* < 1$), upper ($1 \geq U^* \leq 2.5$) and lower ($U^* > 2.5$), being
 420 the maximum value of $\hat{\Theta} \simeq 0.7^\circ$, reached at $U^* = 1.41$ within the upper branch. However, this distinction must
 421 be considered carefully here due to scarcity of data. The frequency response of flaps is analyzed with help of
 422 Fig. 5(c), where the ratio $f^* = f_p/f_n$ is depicted (the characteristic frequency of plates oscillation f_p is obtained
 423 by taking the Power Spectral Density Transform of instantaneous angular displacement). Additionally, the
 424 Strouhal linear law given by the vortex shedding behind the rigid case, i.e. $f^* = St_w^r U^* = 0.29 U^*$ has been
 425 included for comparison. The oscillations frequency of plates is seen to follow in general the Strouhal law
 426 given by the rigid cavity (St_r), indicating that the wake dynamics mostly governs the frequency response of
 427 the plate. Interestingly, the values of f^* are above the linear law around $U^* = 1$, defining a sort of plateau,
 428 where the upper branch of amplitude response rises. This might be an indication of plates responding close to
 429 their natural frequency in water. Note that no valid free-decay tests are available for plates in water, as the
 430 motion is quickly damped; nevertheless, a simplified theoretical estimation of the natural frequency in water
 431 as $f_{n,w} = (1/2\pi)\sqrt{k/(J + J_w)}$, where J_w is the polar moment of inertia of the displaced volume of water,
 432 provides values of $f_{n,w} \leq f_n/3$ (this approximation does not consider any added mass coefficient and therefore,
 433 its use for a deeper analysis of results has been discarded). Besides, the value of f^* for plates oscillations lies
 434 also above the linear law of $St_w^r U^*$ at large values of U^* . This was also reported by García-Baena et al.
 435 (2021b) for flexible foils, where it is discussed that the shedding process accelerates as the distance between
 436 rear edges of plates decreases resulting from the progressive reconfiguration with increasing U^* .

437 Once the response of plates has been analyzed, it can be concluded that the dynamic response of flaps
 438 within the range of U^* considered herein is very weak (notice that the amplitude of oscillations $\hat{\Theta}$ represents
 439 at most 15% of the mean angular displacement Θ at $U^* = 1.413$ and only a 4% for $U^* = 3.48$), and therefore,
 440 the self-adaption can be treated as quasi-static in a first approximation. This may simplify the adaptation of
 441 this type of strategy as drag reducer in more complex applications involving, for instance, bluff vehicles.

442 Considering now the results on the deflection of plates under cross-flow, Fig. 5(a) depicts the evolution of
 443 time-averaged displacement Θ for both the windward and leeward plates. As observed, the plates' displacement
 444 remains nearly zero for $U^* \leq 1$ and grows abruptly around $U^* = 1$, which has been approximately identified
 445 as the threshold of instability for the plates' departure from equilibrium. It is seen that the maximum mean
 446 deflections are approximately 4.2° and 2.9° for the windward and leeward plates respectively. Note that such
 447 values represent the relative displacement with respect to the initial positions of equilibrium (which are already
 448 yawed 4°). Thus, if the trends are analyzed closer, it can be observed that the windward plate features an
 449 asymptotic evolution that tends to reach the limit of 4.2° at high values of U^* . Considering that this value
 450 is a relative displacement, such result is an indication of the plate's alignment with the flow, compensating
 451 the initial yaw angle of $\beta = 4^\circ$. Besides, the leeward plate displays an increasingly growing trend at large
 452 U^* . Thus, although the maximum value of the corresponding Θ is 2.9° at $U^* = 3.48$, this trend suggests
 453 a larger adaption of plates to flow outside the range of reduced velocity studied here (note also that the
 454 equilibrium angular position of the leeward plate for the rigid case under cross-flow is already pointing inwards
 455 in the transverse direction to the flow, so that the deflection of the flexible plate may be viewed as an extra
 456 reorientation with respect to its initial *tilted* position, what would lead to an effective value of nearly 7°). In

Figure 7: Time-averaged contours of axial velocity $U_x(x_o, y_o)$ and corresponding streamlines for $\beta = 4^\circ$ and (a) $U^* = 0$, (b) $U^* = 1.15$, (c) $U^* = 3.48$. An estimation of flaps location and orientation has been included for illustration purposes.

any case, the alignment of the windward plate with the flow and the extra increase in Θ for the leeward plate, are seemingly associated with the intense relative reduction of the drag coefficient at large U^* displayed in Fig. 4 (a) for $\beta = 4^\circ$. Finally, it is interesting to note that the side force and, consequently, the global drag seem to be particularly sensitive under cross-flow conditions to the amplified vibration response of the plates reported for $U^* = 1.41$ (Fig. 5a), for its value is clearly enhanced for such configuration of plates (Fig. 4a).

4.4. Near wake visualizations

The modifications of the near wake topology induced by the quasi-static deflection have been evaluated with the help of PIV measurements, performed for selected values of the reduced velocity. First, the effect of the mean plates displacement on the recirculating length is discussed with the help of the time-averaged contours of the axial velocity, $U_x(x, y)$, and the corresponding streamlines, depicted in Fig. 6, for $U^* = 0$, 1.15 and 3.48 and aligned conditions, $\beta = 0^\circ$. It is observed that the progressive mean displacement of plates reduces the size of the recirculating bubble. The deflection induces the flow to leave the rear edges with a higher momentum towards the axis in the y coordinate, resulting into a decrease of the transverse height or bluntness and the shortening of the recirculating bubble with increasing U^* . The modification of the structure of the near wake also reduces the backflow velocity, $U_x < 0$.

On the other hand, the effect of the plates' self-adaption under cross-flow on the near wake is shown in Fig. 7, with help of the corresponding time-averaged contours of axial velocity and flow streamlines for $\beta = 4^\circ$ and the same selected values of U^* used in the previous figure. As observed, the body misalignment induces the deflection of the recirculation bubble which becomes asymmetric. In particular, the leeward clockwise vortex becomes bigger and is located closer to the body base than the windward counter-clockwise vortex. When compared to the aligned case of $\beta = 0^\circ$, the cross-flow tends to enlarge the recirculation bubble which extends over a wider region in the near wake, what may translate into a lower general pressure at the wake, and consequently a larger drag. Besides, the size of the bubble and respective cores of recirculation reduces progressively as U^* grows. This process is induced by the gradual deflection of flaps as the stiffness of plates is decreased. Additionally, the unequal mean deflection of both plates induces an increasing global deflection of the streamlines at the rear stagnation point of the bubble (see Fig. 7c).

To quantify the reorientation of flaps as U^* grows, we compute the mean values of the recirculating bubble bluntness, H_r , and length, L_r , from the PIV measurements. The value of H_r is defined as the gap between the external corners of plates rear edges (it can be also easily derived with help of the displacement measurements presented in Fig. 5), while the length L_r is characterized as the maximum downstream location from the body base ($x = 0$) where $U_x \leq 0$ (thus defined, the value of L_r implicitly includes the cavity length). Note that H_r and L_r are given with respect to the rotated local coordinate system Oxy for $\beta = 4^\circ$. The trends with the reduced velocity U^* of H_r and L_r are respectively depicted in Fig. 8(a) and (b). As observed, the variation of H_r with U^* is very similar to that of C_x shown in Fig. 4, especially for $\beta = 0^\circ$, whose initial plates' displacement is stronger. In particular, due to its dependence on the evolution of the time-averaged angular deformation of plates (Fig. 5a), very small changes of H_r take place initially with increasing U^* for the stiffer cases, while a sudden decrease occurs for $U^* > 1$. Note that the the minimum values of H_r at $U^* = 3.48$ for

Figure 8: Main time-averaged magnitudes of recirculating bubble and drag coefficient for $\beta = 0^\circ$ (grey circles) and 4° (white circles): (a) recirculating bubble bluffness H_r and (b) recirculating lengths L_r versus the reduced velocity U^* . (c) Mean drag coefficient versus the bluffness H_r . Numerical results for selected values of U^* are displayed using asterisks, while the solid line in (c) represent the linear fit of eq. 13. (i) Recirculating lengths, defined from flaps' tip, ($L_r - l_c$) evolution with U^* .

494 $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 4^\circ$ are respectively $H_r = 0.73$ and 0.80 . It should be noted that the trends of H_r for both
 495 values of β diverge initially as the adaption of plates is slightly stronger at low values of U^* for $\beta = 0^\circ$ (see
 496 Fig. 5a), but become nearly parallel for larger values of U^* when the leeward plate adapts to flow for $\beta = 4^\circ$.
 497 In this regard, as expected for a bluffer body with higher drag, the trend of H_r in cross-flow lies above that
 498 corresponding to aligned flow conditions. On the other hand, the recirculating length L_r undergoes a similar
 499 decrease with increasing U^* for both values of yaw angle, featuring a sharp change around $U^* = 1$, where the
 500 mean deflection of plates has been shown to depart abruptly (see Fig. 5b). As we compare rear flaps with the
 501 same length, where the separation point is fixed for all the cases, we can also compute the recirculation length
 502 relative to the flaps' tip, $L_r - l_c$. The evolution of this distance is depicted in Fig.8(i).

503 Following the discussion introduced by García-Baena et al. (2021b) for the reconfiguration of flexible rear
 504 foils, the impact of the recirculating bubble bluffness on the drag coefficient can be estimated from H_r . In
 505 particular, it was discussed therein that the dependence between both magnitudes can be established by means
 506 of an affine direct relationship, that allows to quantify the connection between near wake and flow separation
 507 and hydrodynamic improvement provided by the trailing edge streamlining. To evaluate whether the same
 508 dependence applies here when flexibly-hinged rigid flaps are used instead of flexible foils, we depict in Fig. 8(c)
 509 the mean drag coefficient C_x versus H_r (there, the results for $\beta = 4^\circ$ are given referred to local coordinate
 510 axis). The results of $\beta = 0^\circ$ and 4° seemingly collapse on a single trend. From here, it is shown that the mean
 511 drag coefficient C_x fairly varies linearly with the near wake bluffness H_r , following the equation

$$C_x = C_{x,ref} + \alpha(H_r - H_{r,ref}), \quad (13)$$

512 where the values of $C_{x,ref} = 0.72$ and $H_{r,ref} = 1$ have been taken from the rigid reference case for $\beta = 4^\circ$ (largest
 513 drag), and α is that maximizing the R-squared fitting coefficient. These results confirm that the reconfiguration
 514 process of flexible foils and flexibly-hinged rigid plates are similar in terms of the direct relationship between
 515 recirculating bubble size and drag, with the bubble bluffness becoming smaller as U^* (or Ca) increases.

516 Another generally accepted result concerning wakes behind blunt-based bodies is that variations of drag
 517 coefficient are proportional to variations of the base suction, defined as the negative base pressure coefficient,
 518 i.e. $\Delta C_x \propto \Delta(C_b)$. Thus, the relation 13 allows a first estimation of the base pressure recovery induced by
 519 reconfiguration of plates. To validate such hypothesis, we next present the numerical results on drag, plates'
 520 deflection and wake pressure.

521 5. Numerical results

522 As highlighted in Sect. 2, two-dimensional turbulent numerical simulations are performed to complement
 523 the experimental study for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and the extended range of reduced velocity $U^* = [0.01, 4.27]$. First, it
 524 will be analyzed whether a simple, unsteady RANS approach is capable of retrieving major variables of the
 525 simplified fluid-structure interaction experimental problem. After such a validation of results, the study will

Figure 9: Time-averaged contours of the pressure coefficient C_p and plates locations obtained from numerical simulations for $U^* = 0.01$ (a), $U^* = 1.13$ (b) and $U^* = 3.33$ (c). Respective values of the base suction coefficients are $C_b = 0.541$ (a), $C_b = 0.526$ (b) and $C_b = 0.469$ (c). C_p values range from -1.5 (blue) to 0.5 (red).

526 help to understand effect of plates' self-adaption on the wake pressure and limits of such process at larger
 527 values of reduced velocity.

528 5.1. Validation of numerical results and limit of plates adaption

529 We first evaluate the capability of two-dimensional simulations to retrieve major results from experiments.
 530 The comparison between numerical and experimental results is done with the help of Figs. 4, 5 and 8. These
 531 figures depict numerical results for: the time-averaged drag coefficient C_x and corresponding relative reduction
 532 with respect to the reference case of rigid static plates, ΔC_x (Fig. 4); mean deflection of plates Θ , amplitude
 533 of oscillations $\hat{\Theta}$ and corresponding frequency ratio f^* (Fig. 5); and size of the recirculating bubble, H_r and L_r
 534 (Fig. 8). As observed in these figures, experimental and numerical results describe nearly identical qualitative
 535 evaluations with the reduced velocity. Besides, depending on the variable, the quantitative comparison between
 536 results shows errors of different magnitude. For instance, values of drag C_x at coincident reduced velocity of
 537 $U^* = 1.41$ sheds a relative errors of 1.5%, while the maximum differences for fitted values between both trends,
 538 2.3%, are obtained at $U^* = 3.48$. It should be remarked that the studied values of U^* are not necessarily the
 539 same for experiments and numerical simulations and therefore respective fits are used to compare results for
 540 some ranges of the reduced velocity. Similarly, the comparison between mean deflection of plates Θ (Fig. 5)
 541 provides a maximum relative error of 5.2% for Θ between fitted values at $U^* = 3.48$ (at coincident $U^* = 1.41$
 542 the error is 3.9%). These small differences are also observable for H_r (Fig. 8a), as it is a derived magnitude
 543 from Θ . However, values of the recirculating length L_r display larger errors (see Fig. 8b), which are close to
 544 10% for all values of U^* presented. Such discrepancies may be judged acceptable considering the simplicity of
 545 the numerical model, based on the two-dimensional assumption and the unsteady-RANS equations. In fact,
 546 this comparison of L_r provides a smaller relative error than that reported in previous study of Carini et al.
 547 (2017) for a similar D-shaped body at $Re = 32000$. Notwithstanding the differences, as shown therein, the
 548 U-RANS flow can be successfully used to predict major features of dominant stability mode, sensitivity and
 549 frequency at the wake.

550 Thus, it can be concluded that the U-RANS simulations render similar results to those obtained experi-
 551 mentally at a relatively low computational cost, despite the fact that the experimental bluff body presents
 552 a finite span in the towing tank, with an aspect ratio $w/h = 7.64$. In general, the agreement between results
 553 from both approaches in term of forces and fluid-structure interaction response, can be considered good, prov-
 554 ing the capability of simple two-dimensional turbulent numerical simulations to obtain a fair estimation of the
 555 major variables from the approximated 2D experimental problem. In this sense, Fig. 4(a) shows also that the
 556 evolution with U^* of the numerical amplitude of oscillations $\hat{\Theta}$ is very similar to the experimental trend for
 557 coincident values of U^* , which displays maximum $\hat{\Theta} < 1^\circ$ at $U^* = 2.13$, and a very weak amplitude at larger
 558 reduced velocity. In addition, this confirms the weaker dynamic response of plates, so that the analysis of the
 559 quasi-static nature of the adaption process seems to be appropriate within the range of U^* selected here.

560 On that account, numerical results may be used to study the extension of results and effect of adaption
 561 of plates beyond the range of experimental reduced velocity. As observed in Fig.5(a), the mean deflection
 562 of plates clearly tends to an asymptotic value of 5.8° , indicating a limit on the self-adaptive process. As
 563 discussed earlier, the computation of the Vogel exponent γ (eq. 12), is typically used to evaluate the effective
 564 reduction of the quadratic dependence of the drag on the flow velocity. Thus, the numerical results on the
 565 drag force and its evolution with the reduced velocity U^* (Fig.4a), allows extrapolation of the Vogel exponent

Figure 10: Time-sequence of vortex shedding depicted by means of instantaneous snapshots of pressure coefficient c_p and corresponding flow streamlines for (a) $U^* = 0.01$, (b) $U^* = 1.13$ and (c) and $U^* = 3.33$.

566 towards higher values of the Cauchy number Ca (Fig. 4c) showing an increase of γ after reaching a minimum
 567 at $Ca = 52.272$. This approximation from numerical results confirms the limit on the potential decrease of
 568 the drag force beyond the range of dimensionless stiffness (either U^* or Ca) analyzed here, and justify the
 569 selection of the values for the present study.

570 5.2. Analysis of the wake pressure

571 To understand the mechanism behind the reported drag reduction induced by the plates' reorientation,
 572 the effect of such process on the near wake pressure is next discussed. In view of the good quantitative
 573 agreement reported between experimental and numerical results for values of C_x and H_r , it seems that the
 574 aerodynamic improvement is mostly governed by the mean plates' deflection Θ (see Fig. 8c and eq. 13), and
 575 the associated pressure modifications induced inside the cavity. To study that, the time-averaged contours
 576 of the pressure coefficient C_p and the mean deflection position of plates for selected values of the reduced
 577 velocity, $U^* = 0.01$, 1.13 and 3.33, are depicted in Fig.9. The mean angular position of plates is also shown to
 578 illustrate the reconfiguration of the trailing edge. Additionally, the corresponding values of the time-averaged
 579 base suction coefficient, $C_b = -\langle C_{p,b} \rangle$, are also listed. First, the three selected values of U^* display the
 580 progressive displacement of plates, starting with a nearly nil mean deflection Θ for $U^* = 0.01$, that becomes
 581 $\Theta = 1.22^\circ$ for $U^* = 1.13$ and $\Theta = 5.21^\circ$ for $U^* = 3.33$. This process is associated with a gradual reduction of
 582 near wake bluntness and recirculating length (see trend of L_r in Fig. 8b). The reduction of the bubble size is
 583 inferred by the shrinking of the intense region of negative pressure. In particular, the local minimum becomes
 584 more negative with the reorientation of plates; however, the pressure inside the cavity recovers and becomes
 585 less negative, what consequently leads to a lower base suction coefficient (note that the base suction is positive
 586 by definition).

587 The reduced extension of the recirculating bubble, associated to the streamlining of the trailing part of
 588 the body induced by the plates self-adaption, affects importantly the formation length and intensity of eddies
 589 pressure. This is shown in Fig. 10, where the sequence of vortex shedding process is depicted for the selected
 590 values of $U^* = 0.01$, 1.13 and 3.33, by means of instantaneous snapshots of the pressure coefficient c_p and
 591 corresponding flow streamlines along half shedding cycle. The case with $U^* = 0.01$ (Fig. 10a) can be considered
 592 as the static reference case, as there is barely no deflection of plates. Thus, the sequence displays the formation
 593 and shedding of the clockwise upper eddy, which is identified by means of streamlines and the locus of low
 594 pressure. In particular, at the beginning of the cycle, $\phi = 0$, a wide counter-clockwise eddy extends over the
 595 whole span between plates' edges, while the upper clockwise eddy starts to form. Subsequently, the upper
 596 eddy starts to widen and the pressure becomes more negative as the intensity of the eddy grows, while the
 597 lower eddy dissipates as it is convected downstream. At $\phi = 3\pi/4$, the eddy covers the whole span between
 598 plates, before being expelled into the wake, where starts to dissipate at $\phi = \pi$.

599 The picture is similar in Fig. 10(b,c), although the reorientation of plates reduces the extension of the
600 eddy. It is seen that the pressure inside the eddy decreases locally, although the stronger displacement of
601 plates prevents the eddy to enter the cavity and reduces their size. Thus, no strong recirculation of flow
602 exists inside the cavity, as seen in Fig. 10(c). Such a dead flow-like region increases the pressure at the base,
603 as inferred from the pressure coefficient contours and values given in Fig. 9, what ultimately translates into
604 the important drag reductions reported in Fig. 4. In particular, the values of drag and suction coefficients
605 computed numerically are seen to follow the relation $\Delta C_x = C_x - C_{x,ref} \simeq 1.3\Delta C_b = 1.3(C_b - C_{b,ref})$. The
606 relation deviates slightly from the linear law of slope 1, an effect that is likely to be due to the closure of the
607 cavity as U^* grows, as the value of C_b only considers the pressure at the base but not the effect of the pressure
608 on the outer sides of deflected plates (Lorite-Díez et al., 2020a). In any case, the linear dependence between
609 drag variations and base suction variations is an expected result for blunt base geometry when the pressure
610 drag is the only source of drag.

611 All in all, it has been shown that the self-adaption of flexibly-hinged rigid plates induces an important base
612 pressure recovery. Therefore, it may represent an effective solution to achieve major drag reductions in bluff
613 vehicles, while avoiding the dynamical complexity displayed by purely flexible foils, and the disturbances that
614 it may induce in terms of side loading and maneuverability.

615 6. Conclusions

616 The present work study the aerodynamics of a D-shaped blunt body that implements rear flexibly-hinged
617 rigid flaps and is subject to a turbulent flow, at $Re = 12000$, for different yaw angles, namely $\beta = 0^\circ$ and
618 $\beta = 4^\circ$. To that aim, different flap-embedded plate properties are considered, which yield associated reduced
619 velocities in the range $U^* = (0, 3.48]$. In particular, the effect of the system on the drag, plates displacement
620 and near wake flow is analyzed, by means of experiments and complementary numerical simulations.

621 The results show that, in the range of U^* herein considered, the plates undergo an inwards quasi-static
622 reorientation, which is symmetric for yaw angles $\beta = 0^\circ$ and asymmetric for $\beta = 4^\circ$. Thus, small mean
623 deformation angles Θ are observed for values of $U^* < 1$, whereas a sharp and monotonic increase of Θ occurs
624 for $U^* > 1$, i.e. for lower values of the hinge stiffness, with an asymptotic trend towards the larger values of
625 U^* . Consequently, a progressive streamlining of the trailing edge is induced for both values of the incident yaw
626 angle β , which translates into significant reductions of the associated mean drag coefficients. Such observation
627 is especially remarkable for $U^* > 1$, with maximum values equal to 18% and 19%, obtained for the most
628 flexible case $U^* = 3.48$, for $\beta = 0^\circ$ and $\beta = 4^\circ$, respectively. While computing the evolution of the Vogel
629 exponent γ to evaluate the effect of the rear configuration on the recirculation bubble aspect ratio, it has been
630 observed that $\gamma \simeq 0$ for low Ca number ($U^* < 1$) but displays negative values for $Ca > 3.423$ ($U^* > 1.154$).
631 The exponent presents an experimental minimum value of $\gamma = -0.21$ at $Ca = 52.272$, the most flexible case
632 experimentally investigated. Furthermore, numerical extrapolation of the Vogel exponent towards larger Ca
633 values yields an increase of γ to an asymptotic value equal to -0.06 , which indicates a limit on the potential
634 reduction of the drag with the increase of flexibility. The analysis of the plates oscillations shows that, within
635 the range of U^* selected here, the self-adaptive process can be considered quasi-static, as the amplitude of
636 angular oscillations is very small when compared to the mean deflection of plates.

637 A close inspection of the near wake reveals that the inwards progressive mean displacement of the plates
638 yields a reduction in the recirculation bubble size. The aforementioned stems from an increase of the flow
639 momentum towards the axis in the y coordinate, which results in a narrowing of the traverse bubble height
640 and shortening of the bubble length. A symmetric evolution of the recirculating bubble is observed for $\beta = 0^\circ$,
641 whereas the bubble becomes asymmetric for $\beta = 4^\circ$, with a larger leeward clockwise vortex. The reduced
642 extension of the recirculating bubble significantly alters the formation length and intensity of the eddies
643 pressure. In particular, it is observed that despite the local pressure decrease in the vortices shed from the
644 trailing edges, the plates reconfiguration reduces the eddies size and prevents them from entering the cavity,
645 thus, creating a dead flow region with a consequent pressure increase at the body base.

646 In summary, the present work shows that the use of low dynamical order, adaptive control systems to
647 reduce the drag of a bluff body and manipulate the wake behind it might constitute an effective alternative to
648 more complex, purely flexible solutions. These solutions are more robust and easier to implement than purely
649 flexible systems, and yield comparable reductions in aerodynamic drag, while circumvent the complex solid
650 dynamics and associated disturbances observed in flexible foils, which renders the former more appealing for

651 engineering applications. In particular, the device herein studied, which consists of flexibly-hinged rigid plates,
652 has been shown to induce significant drag reductions based on trailing edge reconfiguration. These kinds of
653 systems might be of use for both land heavy transport, with air as the working fluid, or ocean applications,
654 with water as the working fluid. On this matter, it is important to highlight that the effect of the density and
655 associated added mass may alter the dynamic response of the flaps, especially in terms of maximum amplitude,
656 which may have direct impact on the maneuverability of vehicle. Additionally, the higher flow velocity in air
657 required to achieve the same Reynolds number defined here, implies that the stiffness of the hinge junction
658 may necessarily rise to increase the natural frequency of the system, and consequently, to keep the reduced
659 velocity within the range of interest ($U^* < 5$) also in air. Hence, some intermediate steps and a thorough
660 study under more realistic conditions (e.g. three-dimensional wake, cross-flow) would be required prior to any
661 applied system is designed and tested in air.

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